

Analysis of challenges of DOAJ-indexing for Diamond Open Access journals within Germany

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1. Executive summary

This report identifies the main challenges of DOAJ indexing faced by Diamond OA journals in Germany. It forms part of DOAJ's agreement with the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft to support the development, visibility, and discoverability of diamond open access journals in Germany. The report brings together two sources: an analysis of DOAJ application rejections for journals from publishers located in Germany from 2020 to 2025, and a qualitative survey of journals based in Germany that are not indexed in DOAJ or that had previously attempted to apply.

The combined activities show that the main obstacles are concentrated in these areas: policy and website documentation; editorial and peer-review transparency; and the capacity of small teams from community-led journals to interpret and implement DOAJ requirements.

The main conclusion is that German Diamond OA journals would benefit from structured support in preparing for DOAJ applications. This support should help journals assess their eligibility, identify gaps in documentation, understand peer-review and endogeneity expectations, and avoid premature or repeated applications.

2. Background

The Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) is a global, community-curated index of high-quality open access journals. It indexes journals that meet defined standards for openness, transparency, editorial quality, and best practice in scholarly publishing.

Many diamond journals are scholar-led, community-based, and operate with limited technical or financial resources. Although they make a significant contribution to equitable and sustainable scholarly communication, they may face challenges in achieving international visibility, demonstrating compliance with recognised publishing standards, and ensuring discoverability within library systems, databases, and research workflows.

Indexing in DOAJ provides an internationally recognised signal of quality and transparency. It improves discoverability through library discovery services, commercial and non-commercial indexing systems, and scholarly infrastructure used by researchers, libraries, funders, and institutions around the world. Inclusion in DOAJ can also help journals demonstrate alignment with funder, institutional, and open science requirements, while strengthening trust among authors, readers, and partners.

This report forms part of the collaboration between the Directory of Open Access Journals and Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) to support diamond open access journals in Germany. The purpose of the collaboration is to enhance and complement DFG's funding programmes through activities designed to:

- make more German diamond open access journals (non-APC and scholar-owned or scholar-led) DOAJ-ready;
- improve the quality assurance, visibility, discoverability, and impact of journals in Germany, particularly DFG-funded journals; and
- strengthen the long-term sustainability and integration of diamond open access journals within the international scholarly communication ecosystem.

The findings in the report contribute to the wider programme of work and will help inform further activities and support for German journals¹ over the remainder of the project.

3. Data sources and limitations

German journals application rejections

The analysis covered rejected German journal applications to DOAJ from 2020 to 2025. The analysis includes rejection rates, major rejection reasons, repeat applications, and subsequent successful inclusion following rejection.

The dataset recorded 144 rejected applications between 2020 and 2025.

The DOAJ rejection dataset is not publicly available because it contains information collected during DOAJ’s application review process. DOAJ’s [confidentiality commitment](#) states that it will “only share or discuss details and information collected during the review process with the applicant or an entity authorised to represent the journal.”

Survey of non-indexed and previously rejected journals

The survey focused on journals in Germany that are not listed in DOAJ or that had previously attempted to apply. It collected evidence on respondent roles, familiarity with DOAJ, prior application status, challenges experienced by previously rejected applicants, general barriers to applying, and desired support.

The survey analysis is based on 35 valid response records. The response period ran from 5 March 2026 to 13 April 2026.

Limitations

The survey sample was relatively small and self-selecting, so its findings should be read as diagnostic rather than statistically representative. However, the overlap between the rejection data and the survey findings provides strong evidence for targeted support priorities.

¹ ‘German journals’ is defined as journals published in Germany

4. Analysis of German journal application rejections (2020-2025)

The following analysis provides key data and insights on German applications for the 2020-2025 period, focusing on rejection trends, repeated applications, and subsequent DOAJ inclusion.

4.1 Key rejection reasons

The data reveals a consistent set of compliance issues that journals face during the application process.

The top five reasons account for a significant portion of all rejections, indicating areas where applicants frequently fail to meet the required criteria.

- Not enough published research: This was the most common reason for rejection, with a total of 30 instances, suggesting a recurring failure to demonstrate sufficient scholarly activity or content volume.
 - According to the DOAJ criteria, journals must publish at least five research articles per year, and newly launched journals need either more than one year of publishing history or at least ten open access research articles before applying.
- Licensing: This category, with 19 rejections, highlights common issues with applicants failing to clearly or correctly state the OA license applied to their content.
 - DOAJ recommends Creative Commons licenses, accepts equivalent publisher licenses in some cases, and states that copyright terms must not contradict the open access license.
- ISSN and Incorrect answers: Tied with 13 rejections each, these point to technical and administrative problems, such as providing an incorrect, provisional, or invalid ISSN or submitting an application with inaccurate information.
 - ISSN must be valid, fully registered and confirmed at the ISSN Portal, and must match the journal website.
- Copyright: With 11 rejections, issues related to the clear ownership and transfer of rights also remain a significant barrier.
 - Copyright terms for published content must be clearly stated, separate from website copyright, and must not contradict the license or OA policy. “All rights reserved” is never appropriate for open access content.

4.2 Trend overview 2020-2025

The data analysed for German applications from 2020 to 2025 show a clear upward trend in both application volume and rejections. Submitted applications have grown from 34 in 2020 to 66 in 2025. Similarly, the number of rejected applications increased from 9 in 2020 to 36 in 2024.

The proportion of rejected applications has also increased during this period. The rejection rate began at 26.5% in 2020 and climbed to 37.7% in 2021. The rate continued to increase, peaking at 57.1% in 2024, meaning over half of all applications submitted that year were rejected. While the total number of submissions was highest in 2025 (66), the rejection rate slightly moderated to 51.5%. Overall, the data show a near doubling of the rejection rate between 2020 and 2025.

This increase in the rejection rate may be attributed to the introduction of additional checks at the Triage² stage, including identifying contradictory copyright information, as well as the implementation of new criteria, including those related to endogeneity and flipped journals.

Chart 1: Submitted vs. Rejected applications (2020-2025)

² Triage is the initial DOAJ application screening stage, where applications are checked for key compliance issues before proceeding to full editorial review.

Year	Applications	Rejections	Rejection Rate (%)
2020	34	9	26.5
2021	53	20	37.7
2022	52	19	36.5
2023	58	26	44.8
2024	63	36	57.1
2025	66	34	51.5

Table 1: Number of submitted and rejected applications of German journals (2020-2025)

4.3 Multiple applications

A notable finding in the application history is the frequency with which journals reapply after an initial rejection. Analysing the full application dataset, a substantial proportion of journals attempted entry more than once, underscoring publishers' determination to gain inclusion.

Over 16% of journals applied multiple times during this period, consuming resources at both the journal and DOAJ, suggesting a lack of clarity on how to address initial compliance failures.

For example, one particular journal applied on three occasions:

First Rejection (Jun 2024): Reason: Licensing

Second Rejection (Jul 2024): Reason: less than 6 months since last application

Third Rejection (Mar 2025): Reason: Endogeny

As of May 2026, this journal has a fourth ongoing application in DOAJ.

This example illustrates that a single journal can be rejected for different reasons across multiple submission attempts, reflecting DOAJ's policy of rejecting journals that do not meet significant criteria (for example, copyright) before more detailed criteria (for example, endogeny) have been checked.

To address this, DOAJ is currently improving transparency around its decision-making criteria and processes, clarifying common rejection reasons, and improving the visibility of guidance materials.

4.4 Success rate of initially rejected journals

An analysis of the 144 journals rejected between 2020 and 2025 shows that approximately 20% (n=144) were later added to the index, indicating that rejection is not always a final barrier to inclusion and can encourage journals to improve their publishing standards.

4.5 Original rejection reasons for successful journals

For journals that were eventually successful in their applications, the most common original rejection reasons were issues that could be addressed through administrative changes or clearer information:

Not enough published research (5 journals)

Copyright (5 journals)

ISSN (4 journals)

The fact that *Not enough published research* is a top original reason for successful journals suggests that many merely needed time to build up the amount of content published or reach the required article volume before re-applying successfully. Similarly, copyright and ISSN issues are often resolved through clearer policy statements or technical fixes.

4.6 Rejection data conclusion

The primary challenges for German journals applying for inclusion relate to technical compliance, clear policy documentation, and sufficient publication volume. The high rate of repeat applications, together with the fact that nearly one fifth of initially rejected journals were later accepted, indicates a need for clearer guidance and stronger support during the initial application phase.

Several journals that were initially rejected at the triage stage for reasons such as not enough published research or ISSN-related issues were subsequently accepted into DOAJ. This suggests that many rejections were due to correctable shortcomings rather than fundamental eligibility concerns. To address this, DOAJ now includes explicit wording in triage decisions encouraging journals to reapply as soon as these particular issues are resolved, without waiting for the standard 6-month period.

The 16 per cent repeat application rate represents a considerable administrative burden for both journals and DOAJ. Repeated unsuccessful submissions may indicate that some journals do not allocate sufficient time to review the criteria, guidelines, and previous feedback in detail.

5. Survey analysis

5.1 Methodology

The survey (included in Appendix A) consisted of 12 questions and one optional contact question. Contact details were excluded from this analysis.

The survey contained routing logic. Respondents who had applied to DOAJ and been rejected were asked detailed questions about their experience preparing the application. Respondents who had not applied, had not considered applying, or did not know whether the journal had applied were taken directly to the general barriers and support-needs questions. The routing is visible in the survey form, where those who had not applied were directed to question 11.

The analysis is based on 35 valid response records collected in a Google Forms response spreadsheet. The response period ran from 05 March 2026 to 13 April 2026. The survey was distributed publicly through DOAJ communication channels. The main call was published on the DOAJ Blog on 5 March 2026 in both English and German, with direct links to the English and German versions of the questionnaire. DOAJ also promoted the survey through its social-media channels, such as LinkedIn and Facebook.

Invitations and reminders regarding the survey invitation were sent via the digital email distribution lists IP_OA_forum and OATP. IP_OA_forum is for the German-speaking Open Access community and is an important resource for library and information science professionals who exchange information on scholarly publishing. It is a moderated discussion group and is operated by the *open-access.network* consortium. This decentralised, nationwide collaborative project is currently supported by five major institutions (Communication, Information, and Media Centre of the University of Konstanz; Open Research Office of the Free University of Berlin; Göttingen State and University Library; German National Library of Science and Technology, Hanover; Helmholtz Open Science Office, Potsdam).

The OATP mailing list distributes content from the Open Access Tracking Project (OATP). This global crowdsourcing project, initiated by the Harvard Open Access Project, collects and organises current news, articles, and discussions about open access to scholarly literature.

For the whole-sample questions, the base is $n=35$. For questions answered only by previously rejected applicants, the base is $n=13$.

Both the English and German versions of the survey are included in Appendix A. Appendix B shows a summary of the responses. Because several questions allowed multiple answers, percentages for multiple-choice questions should not be interpreted as adding up to 100%. Instead, they show how many respondents selected each issue.

German answer categories were translated into English (with an automatic translation tool) for reporting. Counts for multiple-response questions were produced by exact matching of the exported German option text.

5.2 Responses

Respondent profile and application status

Role	Responses	% of total
Publisher/publishing representative	12	34%
Technical/editorial support	6	17%
Editor-in-chief	5	14%
Managing editor/editorial lead	4	11%
Editorial board/team member	4	11%
Other	4	11%

The respondent profile suggests that the results draw on a mix of editorial, publishing, and support perspectives rather than only editors-in-chief. This is important to note as several barriers concern website configuration, policy documentation, and workflow description, which often span multiple roles.

Familiarity with DOAJ

Respondents were generally familiar with DOAJ and its inclusion criteria. On a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means “not familiar at all” and 5 means “very familiar”, 26 of 35 respondents selected either 4 or 5.

Familiarity score	Responses	% of total
1	4	11%

2	1	3%
3	4	11%
4	14	40%
5	12	34%

Application status

Of 35 respondents, 13 had applied to DOAJ and been rejected, while 12 had not applied but considered doing so. This means that 25 respondents, or 71%, had either applied or considered applying.

Application status	Responses	% of total
Applied, but the application was rejected	13	37%
Not applied, but considered applying	12	34%
Not applied, and not considered applying	5	14%
Do not know	5	14%

Findings from previously rejected applicants

The following sections are based on the 13 respondents whose journals had previously applied to DOAJ and been rejected.

Understanding of DOAJ's Open Access definition

Most rejected applicants found DOAJ's definition of full Open Access clear.

Clarity of DOAJ's OA definition	Responses	% of rejected applicants
Very clear	9	69%

Somewhat clear	4	31%
Unclear	0	0%

Open Access statement

Just over half of the rejected applicants reported no challenges with providing a compliant Open Access statement. However, a significant minority did not know what wording was required.

Challenge	Responses
No challenges	7
Did not know the required wording	4
Website technical limitations	2
Other	1

ISSN-related issues

ISSN-related issues were not a major barrier in the rejected-applicant group. Most respondents indicated that this part of the application was easy to answer.

Licensing

Licensing was not the largest barrier overall, but several respondents reported challenges relating to Creative Commons licences or the way licence information is displayed.

Licensing challenge	Responses
No challenges	7
Unsure which Creative Commons licence to choose	2

Licence information not consistently displayed per article	2
Licence not shown in all formats	1
Other	1

The additional responses in English added nuance to this point. One respondent reported that the journal was told it had not provided enough information about its licence, even though it used Creative Commons. This suggests that some journals understand licensing in principle, but do not display licence information in a way that is sufficiently complete, consistent or visible for DOAJ review.

Copyright

Copyright was not a prominent issue for rejected applicants.

Peer-review process

Peer review was one of the clearest problem areas in the survey. The survey asked about informal or developing peer-review processes, difficulty distinguishing editorial review and peer review, endogeneity risks, and lack of written peer-review guidelines.

Peer-review challenge	Responses
Risk of endogeny	6
No written peer-review guidelines	3
Editorial review vs peer review unclear	3
No challenges	3

Process informal or evolving	2
Other	2

The findings suggest that journals may struggle to describe peer review in a way that demonstrates independence, transparency and quality control to an external reviewer.

Editorial information on the website

Publication timelines were the most difficult editorial information for rejected applicants to provide clearly.

Barriers to applying to DOAJ

All 35 respondents answered the general barriers question. Respondents could select more than one answer. The survey included barriers such as a lack of knowledge of DOAJ, unclear requirements, time and staffing constraints, a lack of technical expertise, licensing uncertainty, peer-review documentation, language barriers, insufficient published research content, previous rejection, and a lack of perceived benefit.

Challenge	Responses	% of all respondents
Lack of time or staff capacity	12	34%
Insufficient published research content	10	29%
Difficulty documenting peer review	9	26%
Unclear DOAJ requirements	8	23%

Other	5	14%
Did not know what DOAJ is	4	11%
Uncertainty about licensing/copyright	4	11%
Previous rejection discouraged reapplication	4	11%
Lack of technical expertise	3	9%
No perceived benefit	2	6%
Language barriers	0	0%

The results show that the most common barrier is capacity. Journals may recognise the value of DOAJ indexing but lack the staff time or resources to prepare an application.

The second most common barrier, insufficient published research content, points to a structural challenge for new or low-volume Diamond Open Access journals. These journals may be committed to good publishing practices, but may not yet meet expectations regarding the number of research articles published.

The third and fourth most common barriers, peer-review documentation and unclear DOAJ requirements, are more directly addressable through guidance, templates and support.

Notably, language barriers were not selected by any respondents, suggesting that the English-language application form does not pose a problem.

Support needs

All 35 respondents answered the question on support needs. The survey asked which support or information would most help journals apply or reapply to DOAJ, including clearer explanations, modular guidance, examples, pre-submission feedback, technical support, licensing/copyright support, German-language webinars and one-to-one support.

Support need	Responses	% of all respondents
Clearer explanation of DOAJ requirements	21	60%
Pre-submission readiness feedback	18	51%
Examples of compliant or comparable websites	17	49%
Modular guidance for main sections	14	40%
One-to-one support	10	29%
Training/webinars in German	7	20%
More internal staff/time/resources	7	20%
Technical support	6	17%
Support on licensing/copyright	4	11%

Other	2	6%
No plan, regardless of support	0	0%

Support needs closely mirror the barriers. Respondents asked for clearer explanations, examples, a way to check readiness before submission, and practical help broken into manageable parts.

6. Final recommendations

1. Create a German language DOAJ support pack.

A German-language checklist on the application criteria to DOAJ, easily understandable explanations of the criteria and a step-by-step guide to preparing the application will be provided.

2. Develop modular guidance for key website sections.

Modular guidance would enable publishers, editors, and journal website operators to compile information on various topics clearly and consistently. This would be based on DOAJ's application guidelines and supplementary information (such as more detailed explanations on the blog or in other training materials). The modules would be designed as independent yet flexible building blocks to provide input on topics such as: Open Access statements, licence display, copyright, peer review, editorial governance, publication timelines, author charges/no-fee statements, ISSN, etc.

3. Offer pre-submission feedback.

A full pre-assessment of applications would be too resource-intensive. However, a light-touch readiness review could determine whether a journal should apply now, wait, or first fix specific issues. For this, a guideline for this light-touch review needs to be created to inform potential applicants of the exact requirements before they make contact. After reviewing the journal's or publisher's inquiry, focused consultation regarding specific elements is conceivable.

4. Clarify reapplication.

Guidance should explain when immediate reapplication is appropriate, when waiting is advisable, and how to avoid repeating the same mistakes.

Therefore, in the future, particular attention will be paid not only to stating the reasons for rejection but also to providing an explanation within the respective context. This will give applicants a more precise understanding of the weaknesses and areas for improvement. Follow-up contact will also be simplified.

As an example, the following procedure can be outlined for the project's implementation: Rejected applications are provided with reasons and supporting evidence (for example, regarding specific URLs or wording on the applicant's website). After adjusting these points, candidates can contact the German Managing Editor. The editor reviews whether the changes are adequate and whether further changes are needed. Once acceptable, the application process can be restarted.

It is important to notice that the application will always undergo the multi-stage review process (Triage - Associate Editors - Group Editor - Managing Editor). This ensures that all criteria are carefully reviewed. Prior contact does not automatically indicate that journals will be included in DOAJ.

5. Track recurring support questions.

Questions and recurring issues raised by journals should inform improvements to guidance materials over time. Common themes can help identify where clearer explanations, examples, templates, or additional support are needed, ensuring that future materials address the practical challenges journals face when preparing DOAJ applications.

Appendix A: Survey

Questionnaire in English: <https://tinyurl.com/DiamondJournalsGER>

Survey: Obstacles to Applying to the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)

This survey is aimed at DFG-funded open access journals and other non-DOAJ-indexed diamond open access journals within Germany.

Its aim is to better understand the practical, technical, and conceptual challenges journals face when applying to DOAJ, in order to improve guidance and support.

Participation is voluntary.

The survey is anonymous. No personal data are collected unless you choose to provide optional contact details at the end. The data will be stored in a Google Sheet in DOAJ's Google Drive. See DOAJ's [privacy policy](#) for the full details.

Thank you for your participation. Please do not hesitate to contact us if you have any questions.
helpdesk@doaj.org

Estimated time: 10 minutes

Q1. What is your primary role in the journal?

(Multiple choice- check boxes)

- Editor-in-chief
- Managing editor
- Editorial board member
- Publisher
- Technical/editorial support staff
- Other (please specify) (open text)

Q2. How familiar are you with DOAJ and its inclusion criteria?

<https://doaj.org/apply/guide/>

(Likert scale: Not at all → Very familiar)

Q3. Has your journal ever applied to DOAJ?

- Yes, but the application was rejected
- No, but we have considered applying
- No, we have not considered applying
- Don't know

Q4. Understanding DOAJ's OA definition

Please read the OA definition: <https://blog.doaj.org/2020/11/17/what-does-doaj-define-as-open-access/>

How clear is DOAJ's definition of "fully open access" to you?

- Very clear
- Somewhat clear
- Unclear

Q5. When you were preparing your application, which challenges did you face in providing a compliant Open Access statement on your website?

(Multiple answers possible)

- We did not know what wording was required
- Technical limitations of the website
- No challenges
- Other (free text)

Q6. ISSN issues. When preparing your application it was difficult to know...?

(Multiple answers possible)

- Whether the ISSN was registered
- The difference between print and online ISSN
- Whether the ISSN was provisional and not confirmed
- Nothing, it was very easy to answer.
- Other (free text box)

Q7. When preparing your application to DOAJ, which challenges did you face when specifying the journal's license(s)?

(Multiple answers possible)

- Unsure which Creative Commons license to choose
- Journal uses a custom license, which was hard to describe
- License information not consistently displayed per article
- My journal does not display licensing information in all formats
- No challenges
- Other (free text)

Q8. When preparing your application, was it difficult to determine or explain who retains copyright?

- Yes (optional comment)
- Somewhat (optional comment)
- No

Q9. When preparing your application, which challenges did you face about your peer review process?
(Multiple answers possible)

- Peer review process is informal or evolving
- Difficulty distinguishing [editorial](#) vs [peer review](#)
- Risk of reviewer/author [endogeny](#)
- No written peer review policy
- No challenges

Q10. When checking the inclusion criteria, which editorial information was hardest to provide clearly on the website?

(Multiple answers possible)

- Aims & Scope
- The names and affiliations of the Editorial Board
- Instructions for Authors
- Publication timelines
- None of the above

Q11. Which of the following have been challenges to applying to DOAJ?
(Multiple answers possible)

- I do not know what DOAJ is
- Unclear understanding of DOAJ requirements
- Lack of time or staff capacity to prepare and submit an application
- Lack of technical expertise to prepare the website for submission
- Uncertainty about licensing and copyright requirements
- Difficulties documenting peer review processes
- Insufficient amount of published research content
- Language barriers (application in English)
- Previous rejection discouraged re-application
- No perceived benefit in being listed in DOAJ
- Please describe any additional challenges related to DOAJ applications, or that prevented you from applying. (open text)

Q12. What support or information would most help your journal to apply or reapply to DOAJ?

(Multiple answers possible)

- Clearer explanation of DOAJ requirements
- Smaller unit support for main sections (e.g. for policies, transparency statements)
- Examples of compliant or comparable journal websites

- Pre-submission feedback on eligibility or readiness
- Technical support (e.g. website structure, metadata, platforms)
- Support with licensing and copyright issues
- Training or webinars (in German)
- One-on-one support
- More staff time or internal resources would be required
- I do not plan to apply or reapply, regardless of available support
- Other (please specify): _____

Q13. Optional contact. Would you like to be contacted for support offers?

Yes. Please enter your email.

No

Note shown in form:

Providing contact details is optional and does not affect the anonymity of survey responses.

Questionnaire in German: <https://tinyurl.com/DiamondJournalsDE>

F1. Was ist Ihre primäre Rolle bei der Zeitschrift?

- Chefredakteur:in
- Redaktionsleitung/ Managing editor
- Mitglied des Redaktionsbeirats/ Redaktionsteams
- Herausgeber/ Verlag
- Technisches/ redaktionelles Support-Personal
- Sonstiges:

F2. Wie vertraut sind Sie mit dem DOAJ und seinen Aufnahmekriterien? <https://doaj.org/apply/guide/>

Überhaupt nicht vertraut → Sehr vertraut

F3. Hat sich Ihre Zeitschrift jemals beim DOAJ beworben?

- Ja, aber die Bewerbung wurde abgelehnt.
- Nein, aber wir haben eine Bewerbung in Erwägung gezogen.
- Nein, wir haben eine Bewerbung nicht in Erwägung gezogen.
- Weiß ich nicht.

F4. Verständnis der Open-Access-Definition des DOAJ

Bitte lesen Sie die folgende OA-Definition:

<https://blog.doaj.org/2020/11/17/what-does-doaj-define-as-open-access/>

Wie klar ist die DOAJ-Definition von „Full Open Access“ für Sie?

- Sehr klar
- Einigermaßen klar
- Unklar

F5. Als Sie Ihre Bewerbung vorbereitet haben: Mit welchen Herausforderungen waren Sie konfrontiert, um eine richtlinienkonforme Open-Access-Erklärung auf Ihrer Website bereitzustellen? (Mehrfachantworten sind möglich)

- Wir wussten nicht, welche Formulierung erforderlich war.
- Technische Einschränkungen der Website.
- Keine Herausforderungen
- Sonstiges:

F6. ISSN-bezogene Probleme: Bei der Vorbereitung Ihrer Bewerbung war es schwierig zu wissen, ... (Mehrfachantworten sind möglich)

- ob die ISSN registriert war.
- was der Unterschied zwischen Print- und Online-ISSN ist.
- ob die ISSN vorläufig und noch nicht bestätigt war.
- Nichts, es war sehr einfach zu beantworten.
- Sonstiges:

F7. Mit welchen Herausforderungen waren Sie bei der Vorbereitung Ihrer Bewerbung konfrontiert, als Sie die Lizenz(en) der Zeitschrift angeben mussten? (Mehrfachantworten sind möglich)

- Es gab Unsicherheiten darüber, welche Creative-Commons-Lizenz zu wählen ist.
- Die Zeitschrift verwendet eine eigene (individuelle) Lizenz, die schwer zu beschreiben war.
- Lizenzinformationen werden nicht einheitlich pro Artikel angezeigt.
- Meine Zeitschrift zeigt Lizenzinformationen nicht in allen Formaten (Ausgaben oder Artikel) an.
- Es gab keine Herausforderungen.
- Sonstiges:

F8. War es bei der Vorbereitung Ihrer Bewerbung schwierig, zu bestimmen oder zu erklären, wer das Urheberrecht (Copyright) behält?

Bitte erläutern Sie Ihre Angabe bei Bedarf im Feld Sonstiges.

- Ja
- Teilweise

- Nein
- Sonstiges:

F9. Mit welchen Herausforderungen waren Sie bei der Vorbereitung Ihrer Bewerbung in Bezug auf Ihren Peer-Review-Prozess konfrontiert? (Mehrfachantworten sind möglich)

- Der Peer-Review-Prozess ist informell oder (noch) in der Entwicklung.
- Schwierigkeiten, zwischen redaktioneller Prüfung (Editorial Review) und Peer Review zu unterscheiden.
- Dem Risiko von Endogenität (Reviewer/Autoren aus dem eigenen Umfeld).
- Es gab/ gibt keine schriftlich fixierten Peer-Review-Richtlinien.
- Keine Herausforderungen

F10. Bei der Überprüfung der Aufnahmekriterien: Welche redaktionellen Informationen waren auf der Website am schwierigsten klar darzustellen? (Mehrfachantworten sind möglich)

- Ziele und Fachbereich (Aims & Scope)
- Namen und institutionelle Zugehörigkeit des Redaktionsbeirats (Editorial Board)
- Autor:Innenrichtlinien (Instructions for Authors)
- Publikationszeiträume (Publication timelines)
- Keine der genannten

F11. Welche der folgenden Punkte waren Hindernisse für eine Bewerbung beim DOAJ? (Mehrfachantworten sind möglich)

- Ich wusste/ weiß nicht, was das DOAJ ist
- Unklarheit über die Anforderungen des DOAJ
- Mangel an Zeit oder Personalkapazität, um eine Bewerbung vorzubereiten und einzureichen
- Mangel an technischem Fachwissen, um die Website für die Einreichung vorzubereiten
- Unsicherheit bezüglich Lizenz- und urheberrechtlichen Anforderungen
- Schwierigkeiten bei der Dokumentation von Peer-Review-Prozessen
- Unzureichende Menge an veröffentlichten Forschungsinhalten
- Sprachbarrieren (Bewerbung auf Englisch)
- Vorherige Ablehnung hat von einer erneuten Bewerbung abgeschreckt
- Kein wahrgenommener Nutzen einer Listung im DOAJ
- Bitte beschreiben Sie weitere Herausforderungen im Zusammenhang mit DOAJ-Bewerbungen oder Gründe, die Sie von einer Bewerbung abgehalten haben:

F12. Welche Unterstützung oder Information würde Ihrer Zeitschrift am meisten helfen, sich beim DOAJ zu bewerben (oder erneut zu bewerben)? (Mehrfachantworten sind möglich)

- Klare(re) Erläuterung der DOAJ-Anforderungen
- Unterstützung in kleineren Einheiten für Hauptabschnitte (z. B. für Richtlinien, Transparenzerklärungen)
- Beispiele für konforme oder vergleichbare Zeitschriften-Websites
- Feedback vor der Einreichung zur Eignung oder Bereitschaft
- Technische Unterstützung (z. B. Webseiten-Struktur, Metadaten, Plattformen)
- Unterstützung bei Lizenz- und Urheberrechtsfragen

- Schulungen oder Webinare (auf Deutsch)
- Individuelle Beratung (Eins-zu-eins-Support)
- Es wären mehr personelle, zeitliche oder interne Ressourcen erforderlich
- Ich plane keine (erneute) Bewerbung, unabhängig von der verfügbaren Unterstützung
- Sonstiges (bitte näher beschreiben): _____

F13. Optionaler Kontakt.

Möchten Sie für weitere Unterstützungsangebote kontaktiert werden?

- Ja. Bitte geben Sie Ihre E-Mail-Adresse ein.
- Nein

Appendix B: Survey charts

F1. Was ist Ihre primäre Rolle bei der Zeitschrift?

32 responses

F2. Wie vertraut sind Sie mit dem DOAJ und seinen Aufnahmekriterien? <https://doaj.org/apply/guide/>

32 responses

F3. Hat sich Ihre Zeitschrift jemals beim DOAJ beworben?

32 responses

F4. Verständnis der Open-Access-Definition des DOAJ Bitte lesen Sie die folgende

OA-Definition: <https://blog.doaj.org/2020/11/17/wh...DOAJ-Definition von „Full Open Access“ für Sie?>

10 responses

F5. Als Sie Ihre Bewerbung vorbereitet haben: Mit welchen Herausforderungen ware...

n Sie konfrontiert, um eine richtlinienkonforme Open-Access-Erklärung auf Ihrer

F6. ISSN-bezogene Probleme: Bei der Vorbereitung Ihrer Bewerbung war es schwierig zu wissen, ... (Mehrfachantworten sind möglich)

10 responses

F7. Mit welchen Herausforderungen waren Sie bei der Vorbereitung Ihrer Bewerbung...

konfrontiert, als Sie die Lizenz(en) der Zeitschrift angeben mussten?

F8. War es bei der Vorbereitung Ihrer Bewerbung schwierig, zu bestimmen oder zu erklären, wer das Urheberrecht (Copyright) behält?

10 responses

F9. Mit welchen Herausforderungen waren Sie bei der Vorbereitung Ihrer Bewerbung in Bezug auf Ihren Peer-Review-Prozess konfrontiert? <https://d...control-process> (Mehrfachantworten sind möglich)

10 responses

F10. Bei der Überprüfung der Aufnahmekriterien: Welche redaktionellen Informationen waren auf der Website am schwierigsten klar darzustellen? (Mehrfachantworten sind möglich)

10 responses

F11. Welche der folgenden Punkte waren Hindernisse für eine Bewerbung beim DOAJ?

(Mehrfachantworten sind möglich)

32 responses

F12. Welche Unterstützung oder Information würde Ihrer Zeitschrift am meisten helfen, sich beim DOAJ zu bewerben (oder erneut zu bewerben)? (Mehrfachantworten sind möglich)

32 responses

